

Water services that last

Model report, 21 August 2014

Problem owner: IRC International Water and Sanitation Centre

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Foreword

The report before you has been written to complete a bachelor thesis on the faculty Technology, Policy and Management. The report contains a full description of a model that was simulated to test the water supply system in rural areas of Uganda. The report has been written between march 2014 and July 2014.

I would like to thank Deirdre Casella for the opportunity to do this project and the support and kindness during the project. I would like to thank Kristof Bostoën and Chris Brown for the guidance during the modelling phase and the clear picture they created on what the model should look like and what outcomes it should be able to show.

Thirdly I would like to thank Bert Tielens for helping me learn how to program, start up the modelling and to think more like a programmer. Last I want to thank Igor Nikolic and Pieter Bots for the provision of all the necessary equipment and for all their advice during this period of time.

Delft, 21 July 2014

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Summary

In the rural areas in Uganda there is still a large part of the population that has no access to safe water sources. Currently only 64% of the population in rural areas does have access to safe water sources. In this report we will search for a way to improve the water supply system in Uganda. To improve the water system and to increase the number of people with access to safe water sources we will take a closer look on the number of water points and the repair time of water points. To see how the population can be affected by the change in these variables a model has been build that simulates the current situation in Uganda. The model contains a number of households (in this case the average number of households of a parish in Uganda) and a number of water points. Each household has a water collector that goes out every day to collect water for his household. The model has been simulated so that each water collector will walk to the nearest water point and check if this works. If it does he collects water and returns home with his collected water. If the water point does not work, the water collector will search for the closest water point to his current position and his house. If this water point does not work either he will return home to rest for a while. If a water collector returns home he will check the current amount of water at his house to see if he has enough or if he has to go and get water again. He will do this until 18:30. The water points will keep track of the number of visitors and the number of water that has been taken from them. After a certain amount they will break down and it takes a number of days (approximately 20 days in Uganda) to be repaired. The water collectors keep track of how long they have been from home, so the model can calculate the needed time to collect water. At the end of each day the model calculates the amount of water at the households compared to the needed amount of water per household (depends on the number of residents) and the average time it took to get this water. With this information the households get a service level and a colour. Green is good, yellow is average, orange is bad and red means they have no service. Red means they did not get enough water from a safe water source to satisfy their basic needs. The number of water points in the model and the number of days needed for repair can vary. To see how a different number of water points and different repair times effect the system a couple of scenario's have been tested. The first scenario is the actual scenario in Uganda. The second one has a decrease in repair time, the third an increase in water points and the fourth a combination of the both. The tests show that the change in a number of water points has a larger effect on the service levels and the number of households that have access to safe water points than a change in repair time. Only ten extra water points will give 90,57% of the population in rural areas of Uganda access to safe water sources. This is 26,57% more than the current situation (64%) and a repair time of 10 days instead of 20 gives 85,75% of the population in rural areas access to safe water sources. This shows that the shortage of safe water is not an insurmountable problem and can be dissolved in the near future.

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1. Problem definition and actor identification

The problem definition will show what the exact problem is in this report and how we intend to analyse the problem. Paragraph 1.1 will give an introduction to the situation and the problem. Paragraph 1.2 will give a small description of the problem owner and what the problem owner wants. Paragraph 1.3 will show which actors are involved in the model and why these actors are chosen. Paragraph 1.4 will give an explanation of our role in this project and paragraph 1.5 will explain what software will be used to analyse the problem and why.

1.1 Introduction

Currently the water supply in Uganda does not meet the UN standards of water supply. Still a large part of the global population lives without access to safe water sources (United Nations 2013). Most of these people live in rural areas and often obtain their water from hand pumps, wells or even rivers and lakes. IRC International Water and Sanitation Centre intends to change and improve the water supply system in Uganda. To improve the situation one needs to take a good look at the current situation first. How does the social behaviour of people in rural areas in Uganda affect the population dynamics and in particular the water supply system? And how can a change in either social behaviour or resources change the dynamics of the water supply system? Therefore we want to examine the different possibilities in resources. The main question this report will try to answer is:

How can the water service delivery levels be maximized and effectuated with minimal needed resources?

The resources have been narrowed to water points and the repair of these water points. In this report we will try to analyse the different outcomes of a change in water points and a change in repair time. The model is built to analyse the alterations in water service levels caused by a change in variables.

The main question is divided in the following sub questions:

- How does a change in water points affect the water service levels of the households?
- How does a change in repair time affect the water service levels of the households?

To give a proper answer to these questions a model has been built to obtain understanding of the current behaviour in rural areas of Uganda. The model will be tested with some adjustments to the variables to see if the situation improves or worsens.

The main adjustments in the model that are used to see the difference in water service levels are a change in the number of available water points and the time it takes to repair a water point. The current situation will show how people react if a water point breaks down and at what service level they are at the end of the day. The desired emergent pattern will show which adjustments (repair time vs redundancy vs life expectancy) have the best effects and in what proportion. The service levels are measured by access, which will be measured by the average time it takes to go for water and return home and quantity which will be measured by the amount of water that is collected at the end of the day compared to the needed amount of water per household per day. The quality and reliability will be left out of the model since the model only deals with water points and not rivers or pipelines and so the quality and reliability will be assumed equal at any water point.

The current pattern, a pattern which shows that not enough households have the possibility to gain water from safe water sources, occurs because there is a lack of knowledge and money on the side of the villagers and on the side of maintenance committees.

Villagers don't know whether a pump breaks down and may walk all the way there anyway. Maintenance committees have no awareness of defective pumps either, since there is no easy way to communicate between villagers and other committees. If a water point breaks down, people will move to different water points and water points will become more crowded.

The desired results will show what the perfect balance is between redundant water points and what one is willing to give up for a faster repair of their water points and a higher service level.

1.2 Problem owner

The main problem owner is IRC International Water and Sanitation Centre. IRC wants to improve the water facilities in Uganda. To improve the water facilities one has to look at different levels within a system.

With this model IRC wants to research the bottom layer of the water supply system. Therefore we will be addressing the water problems of the residents of local villages in rural areas in Uganda.

1.3 Involved actors

There are a lot of actors that are involved with water facilities.

But to programme this model we will only look at the local actors that directly influence the water supplies in this model. Since the model is based on parish level, these are the actors that are directly involved;

- households
- water collector
- water points

1.4 Our role

Our role is to program a model that shows how the improved situation can be, what can be gained by an improved situation and how the improved situation can be achieved. We have to show that if there is a good balance between redundant water points and the time of repair, a higher water service level can be accomplished and how. This can be used to show the government or local governments in Uganda why the water facilities need money to improve and how this money should be used. We need to provide insight to local governments and the national government on how their water supply system can be improved.

1.5 Methodology

Changes in the water supply system on sub-county level in Uganda is not something that can easily be tested in real life. The costs would be huge and it would take years to see what the results would be. Therefore a simulation will be built to analyse the effects of small changes within the water supply system on the water service levels of the households. The variables that will be changed are the number of water points and the repair time of the water points (figure 1). The simulation will be a discrete-event simulation. With a discrete simulation one can simulate the behaviour of a complex system as an ordered system of defined events. Discrete simulations often simulate queuing systems. Therefore the water supply system in rural areas of Uganda will be simulated with a software that can be used to model discrete events. Netlogo is the software that we used to simulate the model. An agent-based modelling software.

Figure 1: *Input and output of the mode*

2. System identification and decomposition

The system identification will show how the model is demarcated and what the structure will look like. In the first paragraph we will explain how variables are used within the boundaries of this project. Paragraph 2.2 gives a proper view on the agents that are used in the model with their properties, interactions, states and dynamics. Paragraph 2.3 will show how the environment of the model is built. What the 'world' looks like.

2.1 Inventory

To build a correct model and to get a clear view on how the social behaviour of people in rural areas in Uganda affect the dynamics of the water supply system one needs information on the current status and patterns in Uganda. To simulate this model we will only look at the lowest level of the water supply system, the sub-county. The parishes that will be reconstructed will only consist of households, water collectors and water points. All the other actors such as parish chiefs, hand pump mechanics and health assistants will be left out of the model to simplify the process and to see what exactly happens if a water point breaks down and how only this affects the households.

On average a parish in Uganda contains about 4644 people and 6 residents per household (Uganda Bureau of statistics, 2002). The service level will be calculated by the number of water that is collected at the end of the day and the time it took to collect water.

The amount of water to get basic service is approximately 15 litres per person per day, 20 litres is needed to cover basic hygiene and food. In this model we will state that every resident per household needs fifteen litres of water per day (Batchelor, C. and Moriarty, P., 2011). If this requirement fails more than 50%, there is no service at the household.

At the age of 13 children can often carry as much water as adults, approximately twenty litres (Sigita, E. W., 21 June 2005). If they are younger they won't be able to carry that much so the average a water collector in this model will be able to carry is fifteen litres plus a random number under six.

The accessibility of a water point will be measured by the time it takes to reach a water point, get water and return to their home. If this takes less than ten minutes (Batchelor, C. and Moriarty, P., 2011) and there is enough water at the end of the day, a household has high service (service level 1) in the model and the house will turn green. If it takes less than sixty minutes and there is enough water, the house has basic service (level 2) and turns yellow, more than sixty minutes and there is enough water, the household has a sub-standard service (level 3) and turns orange. If there is less than 50% of the needed water available the household has bad service (level 4) and turns red. A bad service level is called no-service in the model since the households will have to get water from unprotected rivers and lakes.

People leave their houses randomly between 6:00 a.m. and 7:00 a.m. and want to get back before dark. Therefore the water collectors will start returning to their homes between 18:30 p.m. and 20.00 p.m..

If there is not enough water at the household yet they will go for water again and again until it is getting dark.

The time it takes to pump water is approximately one minute since the pumps have a capacity to lift at least fifteen litres per minute (Whitehead, V., May 2001).

The last information which is relevant to this model is that normally a minor breakdown of a pump occurs after 90.000 litres have been extracted from a water point, a major breakdown after 540.000 litres have been extracted from a water point (Osafo-Yeboah, A., 1994). In this

model we will only look at minor repairs since the model will only run for four months. The minor repairs will be used as a major repair and the pumps will stop working completely.

2.2 Structuring of agents and interactions

The model will be structured in to agents, their properties, their interactions, their states and their dynamics.

2.2.1 Agents

In the model only three agents will be used to simulate the model:

- Hand pumps
- Households
- Water collectors

2.2.2 Properties

Each of the agents contains a number of properties. A property is a variable that the agent carries with him/her and can change if the agent undertakes action such as the amount of water they carry or the number of residents a household has.

The model has some properties that all the agents own, these are called globals. This means that every agent has these variables and agents can read these variables from each other.

The globals in this model are:

- The number of days the model is running
- The current time of the day
- The volume water taken from a pump after which the pump will break down
- The number of pumps that are already broken if the model starts running
- The question whether a household has enough water
- The possibility to give the model a random set up

The world that is built with netlogo consists of small blocks, these are called patches.

Patches can have properties too. In this model patches have the following properties:

- The household density within a radius
- They either have or have no household standing "on" them
- They either have or have no water point standing "on" them

households have the next properties:

- A certain location (a patch they are standing on)
- Amount of water at the household
- A service level (green, yellow, orange or red)
- Number of residents
- Needed water per household
- The number of times they go out to get water
- The start, end and duration of the collection of water

Water points have the next properties:

- A certain location (a patch they are standing on)

- They are either working or defect
- They have the exact time they broke down
- They count the number of water collectors that show up to get water
- They count which number is due to get water
- They count how many water collectors are waiting at the pump
- They count how much water there already has been taken from them

Water collectors have the next properties:

- A home (the house they come from and return to)
- A walking speed
- A status that shows what they are doing (collecting water, standby at home, waiting in queue etc.)
- The location of the water point they will go to
- The time it takes to collect water
- The time the collection is finished
- A ticket number once they get to a water point
- The amount of water they carry
- The maximum time they are willing to wait at a water point
- It will be documented if they have been out to search for a different pump if the queue is too long at one

2.2.3 Interactions

When the model starts to run some agents start to move and interact. Here the interactions of the model will be described to see what the model does exactly.

- Water collectors will leave their houses in the morning to move towards the closest water point.
- If they arrive at a water point, the pump is working and queuing does not take longer than they are willing to wait at a queue, they will wait in line to collect water. The moment a water collector arrives at a water point, the water point gives the water collector a ticket number. They can fetch water when it is their turn (if the turn-number of the water point equals their ticket-number)
- If the water point is defect, the water collector will turn around to search for another working water point which has the closest location to their current location and their home location. If it is getting to late (after 18:30 p.m.) they will return home.
- If the queue at the water point is to long they will turn around to search for another working water point closest to their current location and their home. They will only search for a different water point once and return home after they have arrived at the next water point. Either with water or without. If it is getting to late thy will return home.
- If a water collector is due to fetch water at a water point they will collect water for one minute and they will return home with the water. The water point registers the amount of water that the water collector took and the number of users at their water point. If the total amount of water taken from the water point exceeds the water the water point can give, the water point will break down.
- If the water collector comes back home, he adds the water to the current amount of water of the household. The household will check how long it took to get water and how much water it has. At the end of the day the households will calculate their service levels with this information.
- After the water collector has returned, he checks whether there is enough water at the household. If not he will go again (if time permits it). If there is enough water at the household or

time has passed 18:30 p.m., the water collector will wait standby at home until morning. the interactions are displayed in a process chart in figure 2 paragraph 3.3

2.2.4 States of Agents

Agents can have different statuses during the model run.

Water collectors get a status for their current activity:

outgoing, arriving, queuing, collecting, redirecting, returning, standby at home.

If a water collector is moving from his house to a water point, he is outgoing, if he is waiting at a water point, he is queuing etc.

A household has a certain status to show what their service level is as discussed in paragraph 2.1:

green, yellow, orange or red.

Water points have statuses as well. They get a status for the usage intensity.

If there are less than sixty water collectors at a water point during the day, the water point turns green. For more than sixty users, the water point turns yellow. If there are more than 120 users during the day, the water point turns orange. If the water point stops working it turns red.

2.2.5 Dynamics

In this model only the water collectors are dynamic. They can move within the limits of this parish, within the boundaries of our 'world'. The time frame they will move in, is from dawn (6:00 hours) until the end of the day, which stops at 21:00 so every water collector is back home and the model does not run extra during the night when nothing happens. The model runs 15 hours per day. Every 60 ticks is an hour, so a day is 900 ticks.

The water collecting- day of the water collectors starts at 6:00 and ends at 17:30. After 17:30 they will return home and sleep until the next morning.

2.3 Environment

The environment of this model, the "world" that is created, is an average parish in Uganda, with an average number of residents per household. The number of households and water points can be changed to check out different situations such as larger villages or even city's.

A parish contains on average 774 households with an average of six residents per households (Uganda Bureau of statistics, 2002).

One water point should be able to 'feed' 300 people this means that a parish should contain about sixteen working water points to feed all the people in this village if there are no other resources available.

This model will only use water points as a resource to get water. If households end up at the end of the day with no service level this means that they would go to unprotected sources to get water (rivers, lakes etc.). The households only have one water collector to get water.

The time in the model passes in ticks, but the time of the day and the number of days that have passed are calculated and are displayed on the interface.

The interface shows a couple of variables that can easily be changed. The time it takes to repair a pump, the amount of water that can be taken from the pump until it breaks down, the number of households, the number of clusters, the collection time of the water collectors, the number of pumps that are broken down, the average speed of a water collector and the radius of clusters of households. To test the model, the model will run for three months (model time).

The size of the model is 600 patches by 600 patches. Every patch is 25 meters wide, so the world we created is 15 by 15 kilometres.

3. Concept formalisation

In the last chapter the model has been demarcated. In this chapter the model simulation will be specified. The structure in the data will be explained in paragraph 3.1, In paragraph 3.2 a process chart displays how the system works in a simple figure. Paragraph 3.3 explains the system in a short story; the model narrative, paragraph 3.4 gives an example of the coding for every agent in a part of the pseudo code and paragraph 3.5 describes the use of the model

3.1 Software data structures

The software is build up out of the setup of the model.

First the global variables will be defined, the variables that are properties of all agents.

Second the agents are defined as breeds.

Thirdly the properties per agent will be defined, so every agent has knowledge of a number of variables. After this the setup of the model has to be written. Here one wrights what exactly happens before the model starts to run. The number of agents that need to be created, the initial values of the global variables, the colour of agents or patches, the start-up states of agents etc. In this model the overall setup is quite simple but it refers to setup_waterpoints, households and water collectors. So the setup of the agents is apart from the overall model setup to keep the model structured and simple to understand.

After all the setups the code for 'go' has to be written. This will give the activities of the model, what exactly will happen when you push the button go to run the model. In our model it will run through "determine-time-of-day" until "standby", which are all actions that will be described further down in the model. Also the model stops when there are only two water points left that actually works. Otherwise errors would occur from agents that don't know where to go once they leave their households. This is written as the first activity in the go section.

After the check on water points the model will start running. Determine the time of day, outgoing, collect_water and eventually standby at home.

Every activity is written in the model as a to go command; to setup_watercollectors, to outgoing, to standby etc.

Here the properties of the agents are defined. How will they be calculated and in what kind of units will they be described.

-Globals

Days running: integer >=0

Time of Day: floating point >=6 and <=21

Breakdown Volume: integer >=0

Broken pumps: integer >=0

Enough water?: true/false

Random setup?: on/off

-Patches

household density radius: floating point >=0

patch has household?: true/false

patch has water point?: true/false

-households

Location: xy coordinates of the patch they are on
 Amount of water at the household: integer ≥ 0
 Service level : integer 1/2/3/4
 Number of residents: integer ≥ 1
 Needed water per household (residents*15): ≥ 15
 Times collecting per day: ≥ 0
 The start, end and duration of the collection of water: ticks/ day calculation

-Water points

Location: xy coordinates of the patch they or on
 Working-rate: integer 1/0
 Moment broken: ticks
 Ticket counter: integer ≥ 0
 Turn number: integer ≥ 1
 Queue length (nr of collectors*pumping time): floating point ≥ 0
 Water delivered: integer ≥ 0

-water collectors

Home location: xy coordinates of the household they come from
 Walking speed: integer ≥ 0
 Status: string
 Water point location: xy coordinates of closest water point
 Collection time: floating point ≥ 0
 end of collecting time: floating point ≥ 0
 Ticket number: integer ≥ 1
 Amount of water they carry: integer ≥ 0
 Max queue time: floating point ≥ 0

3.2 Process chart

The process chart shows the process of collecting water by the water collectors
 In paragraph 3.3 the model narrative will simply explain how this figure exactly works.

figure 2: activities of water collectors

3.3 Model narrative

A water collector gets up, goes out to search for a water point, if he finds a water point he checks if the water point is working. If the water point is defect the water collector goes out to search for a different water point. If the water point is working, the water collector checks if there is a queue at the water point. If there is no queue the water collector starts collecting water and returns home to deliver the water. The water will be added to the current amount of water at the household. The amount of water shows what kind of service level that household has. If there is a queue the water collector checks if the queue is too long to wait. If the queue is short enough the water collector will wait for his turn, starts collecting water and returns home to deliver the water.

If the queue is too long, the water collector will leave this water point and goes out to search for a different water point.

The day ends at 17:30 and at 17:30 every water collector will stop doing what he is doing and returns home.

During the day a service level is calculated by time for water collection, amount of water at household and the percentage of water points that is out of order.

3.4 Pseudo-code

The pseudo -code here displays the most important actions of every agent.

For households that is the calculation of the service level, for the water points this is the number of users and when a water point does or does not break down and how it calculates when it broke down. And for the water collectors it shows how a water collector arrives at a water point, starts to queue, collect water and return home.

All households

- calculate their water_service per day
 - set water_service (amount of water/needed water per day)
- the average time it takes to get water per day
 - set average collecting time (total time to get water / collections per day)
- their service level
 - If water service > 50 and average collection time < 60
 - set service level 3
 - set colour orange

All water points

- Calculate the number of users per day (ticket_counter)
- Set moment_broken if working rate is 0
- Calculate queue length ((ticket_counter -turn_number) * collection time)
- Count water delivered
 - set water_delivered water_delivered + carry amount of watercollector

All water collectors

- Set a watercollection_status
 - If patch_has_wp? of patch-here = true and Waterpoint_LocationC = patch-here
 - set watercollection_status "arrived"
- Set max_queue is (20 / 60) (20 minutes)

```
Get ticket_number of water point
    if ticket_number = turn_number set watercollection_status "collectwater"
Get water at a water point
    if watercollection_status = "collectwater"
        set carry_amount 15 + random 6
        set watercollection_status "return_home"
```

3.5 Model Use

The model of water service vs redundancy and repair is a good basic model to show how the number of pumps and the repair time can affect the water service levels. The model was found useful and reasonable. It lives up to the requirements of IRC and contains all the aspects that we agreed on. However the model is a basic model. It does not contain all information that is available. The model only looks at the basic interaction with respect to water supply within a parish. Money and politics have been left out of the model. Also most of the variables in the model are based on approximate values. The model could be extended with formulas that give the right approximation of each value such as the number of residents per household and the number of water collectors per household. Most of the households have more than one collector but in this model the situation had to stay simple. This is the basic model that can be used to implement more complex situations.

This model can help to guide the local or national governments on making decisions with respect to the water supply system, in particular the increase or decrease in repair time or the decision to create a budget to build more water points. But the model has possibilities to grow and help in a lot of other decision making processes within the water supply sector.

4. Model verification

In this chapter the model will be verified. The verification will be divided into four sections. Paragraph 4.1 will contain the recording and tracking of agent behaviour. Paragraph 4.2 will look at a single agent in the model and test the behaviour of this single agent. Paragraph 4.3 will see how the interaction between different agents take place and in the last paragraph the model will be tested on emergent behaviour of multi-agents.

4.1 Recording and tracking agent behaviour

-The first verification test will be a test on the intensity of use of the water points.

If only two pumps are available and there are 774 water collectors, each pump should have more than 120 users per day and turn red.

Also every household should have no service level since the queues are so long that they are not able to get enough water. This seems to be happening (Figure 7 Appendix A).

The second test will show that a water point breaks down after the given breakdown volume.

The volume will be put on $10000 + \text{random } 4000$. This means that somewhere between the delivery of 10000 and 14000 litres the pump must break down. The pump also has to show the exact time it broke down to calculate when it can be repaired. You can see this happening in figure 8 Appendix A.

4.2 Single agent recording

To record of a single agent, the most difficult formula of the model will be tested and the service levels/colours of the households will be tested.

The difficult formula works as followed:

If a water collector arrives at a water point for the first time, he will first have to see if the water point is working. If not, the water collector will be redirected to the closest working water point near their current location and their home location. If the water collector thinks the queue at a water point is too long he will be search for another working water point, closest to his current location and his home location. But once he searches for another he will get a notation that says researched? = true. And he will not re-search again if the queue at the next water point is too long. He will return home. Once he is home again researched? will be false again and the water collector will go out to get water once again. An example of the formula can be found in Appendix A figure 9.

To test if the formula is working one water collector was followed (figure 10 Appendix A). In the pictures one could see that the water collector moves to a water point, sees that the queue is too long, moves to another water point (the water point location they go to changes from (53 31) to (176 -31)), the queue there is too long as well so the water collector changes his status to return-home and starts walking back to his house without any water.

The second test will see how the service levels of the households are calculated. This is a rather simple test.

Different households will be inspected to see if their colour and service levels correspond to the values of different variables of the households.

In figure 11 of Appendix A one can see that household 190 has the colour orange and service level 3.

This means it has more than 50% of its needed water but it took the water collector on average more than 60 minutes to collect water. The average collection time is the total collection time divided by the total collections on one day. So household 190 has an average collection time of a

little over 4 hours.

Household 499 has a service level of 4 and a red colour. This means that it does not have more than 50% of its needed water. They only have 31,4 % of its needed water.

Household 52 has a yellow colour and a service level of 2; More than 50% of needed water (it has 111% and an average collection time of $(2,43/5)$ 0,48 hours which is almost 30 minutes.

So the service levels of the households work correctly.

4.3 Interaction testing in a minimal model

To see how the interaction works we will do two tests.

The first test will be an interaction between water points and water collectors.

The second test will be the interaction between households and water collectors.

The first test will show that if a water collector arrives at a water point, the number of users at the water point will rise by 1. If a water collector has collected water for 1 minute the turn number of the water point will go up and the next water collector can fetch water. Also the delivered water of the water point will rise with the amount of water that was taken by the water collector.

As one can see in figure 9 in Appendix B, five ticks have been followed of a water point. In the second tick a water collector leaves the pump, so the ticket number goes up and the water delivered goes up by the amount of water taken from the pump (this is a random number between 15 and 21). Another water collector arrives at the pump and so the ticket number goes up as well.

In the picture of the fifth tick one can see that another water collector leaves the water point.

The turn number goes up and the water delivered rises.

The second test will show how the water amount at the households rises once a water collector arrives home with an amount of water and how the time it took to collect this water is documented.

A household and a water collector have been followed for two ticks. The tick before the water collector enters the house and the tick the water collector is in the house. One can see that the water amount of household 486 rises from 14 to 29. The collection status of the water collector changes from return_home to standby and his carry_amount goes from 15 to 0.

This works correctly as well (figure 10 Appendix B).

4.4 Multi-agent testing

In multi agent testing the model will be tested on itself. In this test the timeline will be checked and the effect of pumps that break down and how the agents respond to this.

The breakdown volume will be 6000 for this test and the random extra volume 0.

Then we will check the repair time, the repair time will only be 1 day in this test. What you will see is that within 1 day and a little all the pumps start to break down, the queues will be maximum queuing time and the users per day will go down since many people go home because they think the queue is too long. After 1 day the pumps start to work again and the users per day will increase. Figure 14 in Appendix A shows what the situation looks like.

5. Experimentation

The experimentation will be divided into three paragraphs. The first paragraph will determine what the experiments will look like, what timeframe they will be in and what the hypothesis will be.

Paragraph 5.2 will discuss how many experiments will be run on each test and how randomness will be dealt with. The last paragraph will discuss how the experiments will take place, why certain data will be kept and others thrown away and how to check on the consistency of the data.

5.1 Experimentation design aspects

The chapter experimentation design aspects is divided into three parts as well; 5.1.1 Hypothesis, 5.1.2 Timeframe and 5.1.3 scenarios and scenario space.

5.1.1 Hypothesis

The model will be used to see how the water service levels of the households can be improved. Therefore different values of variables will be tested to see how this influences the water service levels. Will we get an emergent pattern on service levels depending on their location? Will we get an emergent pattern on service levels depending on the repair time of the water points? And will we get an emergent pattern on service levels depending on the number of working water points in a parish?

The expectation is that if the repair times become smaller the water service levels will go up and if the number of water points increase the water service levels will go up. The water service levels of the houses nearest to the water points are expected to have higher service levels as well since they need to walk smaller distances.

Therefore an increase of service level is expected with the combination of smaller repair times and a greater number of water points.

5.1.2 Timeframe

The model will be run for four months (120 days/109.000 ticks, 15 hours/ 900 ticks per day) to see how the service levels will be affected. The water points will be repaired after 20 days and the water points will break down after approximately 90000 litres of water has been taken from a water point. The reason the model runs for 120 days is that the water points break down after approximately 10-20 days. After another 20 days the water points will be repaired, this is the cycle that will be run over and over. A model needs to be run at least three times the cycle time. Therefore the run time of 120 days has been chosen. The run time does not include a start-up time. This is because the model starts with a random setup. A random setup means that every household has a random amount of water, each water point has given a random amount of water (so they will break down randomly as well) and a random number of water points is already broken and the exact time they broke down will be chosen randomly as well. Because of the random setup the model start running steady from the start.

5.1.3 Scenarios and scenario space

The scenario's that will be tested will all start in a random setup. With random setup, the start-up time can be skipped and the cycles can start running immediately.

Five different scenarios will be tested. The first scenario is the actual scenario in Uganda. The current situation in Uganda shows that 64% of the population in rural areas have access to save water supplies (Ministry of Water and Environment Republic of Uganda, 2010). After a few tests the scenario was built with 20 water points and a repair time of 20 days.

The second scenario will have a repair time of 10 days, the number of water points stay the same. The third scenario will have the regular repair time of 20 days but the number of water points will change 30 water points. The fourth scenario will be a combination of 15 days of repair time and 25 water points. These numbers were chosen by the problem.

5.2 Experiment setup

By testing the model we found that it took about three to four hours to run a test. Therefore each test will be run only ten times to see how the outcomes of each test vary and if a proper conclusion can be made. It would take too much time to run each test a 1000 times. 13 computers were used to run the tests. The randomness of the model (the delivery of water per water point, the amount a household starts their model run with and the number of pumps that are already broken) only shows that water points have been used before the start of the model run. This gives a more equivalent picture to the actual situation. The households and the water points are randomly placed in clusters. But this gives the opportunity to compare the water service levels to the different locations of the households compared to the water points.

5.3 Experiment execution

The detailed data of each agent and each variable has been executed. So the output does not show what the exact water amount per household is or what the average collecting time of the water collector was. This data has been executed because it gives an overwhelming number of information which takes more time to analyse than the additional value to the tests. Therefore only the graphs and outcomes of the interface will be printed at the end of each test to look at the variation of outcomes.

6. Data analysis

All outcomes will be tested with a correlation test in SPSS to see how the water service levels were influenced by the changes in water points and repair time. The average of the service levels have been taken from each test and these averages have been compared to each other giving an overall average and a standard deviation per test. Since the results fluctuate over the time, all the averages have been taken over the last cycles from 80.000 – 109.000 ticks for every test in every scenario. These averages have been tested to see how they correlate with the change of water points and change of repair time. The outcomes of these tests can be seen in figure 12 in appendix C. The outcomes of the one-sample t-test can be found in figure 21 in appendix C. The R-squared was found to be 0,696 so the data fits the statistic model quite well. All the variables are significant and the standard deviation is small enough to believe that one can make good estimations with this model.

Scenario 1

The scenario shows the current situation in Uganda, 20 water points and a repair time of 20 days. The outcomes of this test show that the average number of people that have access to safe water supplies is 62,33%. This outcome is very close to the 64% which was given by Uganda Water Supply Atlas. The outcomes of the tests show a “badlevellist”. This list keeps track of all the households that have had no access to a safe water supply. The remarkable thing is that almost all households have been without access one time or another (744 length badlevellist figure 3). This means that the service level does not automatically depends on the location of the household. In figure 3 one can see that the number of working pumps and the number of broken pumps fluctuate a little so the average of the last cycles should give a representative result. The average of households with no service in test 1 is 293,8. The average service level is 3,097 (table 1). One can see that the average service level stays stable during the test run (figure 3). The queue lengths increase once the number of broken pumps increase as well and there is a clear link between the number of working pumps and the number of households with access to a safe water source.

Figure 3: results of scenario 1

Scenario 2

The second scenario has a repair time of 10 days and 20 water points. The results can be seen in figure 4. The number of houses with a no service have decreased enormously (figure....). The average of households with no service has dropped to 118,5. This means that 85,75% of the population has access to safe water supplies. The number of working and broken pumps fluctuates a little more than in the first test. The average service level has decreased to 2,955 and stays stable during the run as well. The number of people on the “badlevellist” has decreased as well. This means that “only” 656 people have endured a period without access to safe water sources.

Figure 4: Results of scenario 2

Scenario 3

The third scenario starts with 30 water points and the regular repair time of 20 days. The results can be seen in figure 5. The results of the third scenario are even better than the results of the second scenario. The average number of households with no service level is only 73,6 which is a percentage of 9,43%. So 90,57% of the population in this rural area has access to a safe water source. Unfortunately the number of households with good service level does not increase a lot (only 1 in the final phase) but the “badlevellist” has decreased and the average service level has decreased. In this test one can see that the number of working and the number of broken pumps fluctuates a lot in the beginning of the run. But after approximately 42.000 ticks the outcomes are quite stable. The average service level of this test is 2,914 and at the end of the test there are 576 households on the “badlevellist”.

Figure 5: Results of scenario 3

Scenario 4

The last scenario shows a combination of a decrease in repair time and an increase of water points.

The number of water points is 25 and the repair time is 15 days (results in figure 6). The combination of the two does not improve the conditions compared to scenario 3. However the average number of households with no service level has increased compared to scenario 2 while the average service level has decreased compared to scenario 2. Since the overall access to safe water sources is more important than the average service level, scenario 4 gives better results than scenario 2. But from these test one can conclude that the number of extra water points has more effect on service levels than the repair time of the water points. These results have been tested with a correlation test in SPSS. These test show that the correlation between water points and service level is -0,58 and the correlation between repair time and service level is 0,177 (figure 12 appendix C). The correlation between service level 4 and repair time and water points can be seen in figure 13 appendix C. This shows that the correlation between pumps and service level 4 is -0,675 compared to the correlation between repair time and service level 4 which is 0,290. Table 1 and figure 7 and 8 show the results of each test, compared to the others.

Figure 6: Results of scenario 4

	scenario 1	scenario 2	scenario 3	scenario 4
average number of households with service level 4	293,8	118,15	73,6	82,25
average service level	3,097	2,955	2,914	2,99

table 1 : *The average number of households with no service and the average service level of the households per scenario*

Figure 7: *Histogram of average households with service 4 scenario 1/2/3/4*

Figure 8: *Histogram of average service level scenario 1/2/3/4*

7. Model validation

In this chapter we want to verify if the model displays what we want it to display. Is the model fit for its purpose? Does it answer the questions we asked?

The variables and the values of these variables that are used in the model correspond to the values that are measured in the 'real-world'. Unfortunately this model does not accurately predict the change in water service levels if certain actions will be taken. There are always the interactions of companies, committees and other stakeholders that have not been taken into account in this model. However the model does help to identify patterns and gives a clear view on how the change in water points or repair time does affect the water service levels even if other interactions have not been taken into account. The model gives us insight in the dynamics of behaviour patterns of water collectors in rural areas of Uganda. It is a basic model that still can be expanded and take more matters into account. But the model that has been created is a transparent model and has been validated not only by data but also by experts on the matter (IRC).

Therefore the model is fit to answer the questions we asked and it satisfies the requirements of IRC.

Conclusion

The model has been able to show that the water service levels can be improved by increasing the number of water points or decreasing the repair time of the water points. But most importantly the model shows that the number of households with access to safe water sources can be increased easily if extra sources are placed or the sources would be repaired in less time. The model also showed that the impact of a change in water points has more effect on the water service levels and the number of households with safe access to water sources than the change in repair time. To answer the sub questions. The change in water points affects the water service levels of the households with -0,58 per water point and the number of households with access to safe water sources with -0,675 per water point. The change in repair time affects the water service level of the households with 0,177 and the number of households with access to safe water sources with 0,290 per day of repair time. Then the main question off this report still needs to be answered: *How can the water service delivery levels be maximized and effectuated with minimal needed resources?*

The minimal needed resources will be a combination of water points and repair time. To maximize the service delivery levels there need to be enough water points in a village so that every citizen has got a water point within 5 minutes of their residence which is quite impossible and the resources would not be minimal. But this model has showed that the water service levels can be improved so that a much higher percentage of the population in rural areas has access to safe water sources by building extra water points and reducing the repair time of these water points. If these actions could be accomplished a large part of the global population will live with access to safe water sources.

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Appendix A: Verification test results

Recording and tracking of agent behaviour

Test 1

Here you see the verification of household service levels and the use intensity of water points. In this test there are only two water points working. This gives the following result: Users per water point will be extremely high, all households have bad service and turn red and the queues get extremely long.

Figure 7: only 2 working pumps and no service level

Test 2

In this test you can see that after a pump has delivered 90000 litres it will break down. The picture shows two following ticks. One on tick 4278 where the water delivered is 89985, the working rate 1, the colour orange and the moment_broken 0. The second tick is 4279 where the water delivered has crossed the maximum (90005), the working rate is 0, the colour is red and the moment_broken is 4278.

Figure 8: pump breaks down after pumpvolume has been reached

Single agent recording

Test 1

In this test the behaviour of a water collector is followed. First the water collector walks to a pump with a status “outgoing” and researched? is false. He checks the queue (apparently it is too long) his status will stay “outgoing” but researched? turns to true. Then he walks to the next pump close by and after collecting water his status turns to “return home”. Figure 10 shows the code and figure 11 shows the change in status and researched? and follows the water collector.

```
[if watercollection_status = "re_search"
  [set CollectorCLocation patch-here ; we set the location of the watercollector
   set CollectorHLocation Home_Location ; we set the homelocation of the collector
   set waterpoint_locationC [waterpoint_locationP] of min-one-of
     waterpoints with [(waterpoint_locationP != CollectorCLocation) AND (working-rate = 1)]
     [((Distance CollectorHLocation) + (Distance CollectorCLocation))]
     ; we calculate the minimum distance of a waterpoint
     ; and set this waterpoint as Waterpoint_locationC
   set watercollection_status "outgoing"
   set researched? true]
]
```

Figure 9: coding for re-searching for a water point

Figure 10: redirecting researching and returning home

Test 2

In this test we will check if the water service levels of the households and its colours are correct according to its values. The first household is yellow, has 111% of its needed water and an average collecting time of 29 minutes (total collecting time day * 60 / total collections) so this is correct. The second house is red and has only 31% of its water, this is correct as well. The third household has 110 % of its needed household but its collecting time is 247 minutes. This is bad service and so the colour is orange (Figure 11)

Figure 11: *households and their service levels*

Interaction testing in a minimal model

Test 1

This test shows the interaction between a water collector and a water point.

Figure shows 5 following ticks on which the water point is inspected. In the second tick you see that the ticket number goes up (a new water collector has arrived), the turn number goes up (a water collector has left) and so the water delivered goes up with a number between 15 and 21. Here it goes from 3437 to 3456. It takes 3 ticks to collect water and so in the 5th tick you can see that the water delivered and the turn number go up again.

Figure 12: Interaction between household and water collector

Test 2

In the second test the interaction between a household and a water collector are checked. You can see in figure 13 that a water collector (1467) arrives at his household (486) and then goes into his house. His status turns from “return home” to “standby” and his carry amount goes from 15 to 0. The water amount and the water service of the household go up and the total collecting time and end of collecting time change .

Figure 13: interaction between households and water collector

Multi-agent testing

Test 1

This test will show the how the model works and how all agents respond. There is a very small break down volume for the pumps (6000) and the repair time will be one day. You will see in figure 14 that pumps start breaking down within 1,5 day and do get repaired within a day. You can also see that the users per day per water point go up once more pumps break down and go up once the pumps start working again. Also the queuing length changes enormously, getting higher with less working pumps and dropping down once the pumps start working.

Figure 11: multi-agents testing

Appendix B: Model code

Appendix C displays the model code. After each ; there is an explanation of the previous code-line.

```
globals [                                ; variables owned by all agents
  ref_distance                          ; the scale example: 1 patch = 25 meters
  Days_running                          ; number of days the model is running
  Time_of_day                            ; the current time in hours
  new_ticket                             ; switch variable to set ticket_counter at the same number as
;ticket_number with are variables owned by different turtles
  current_number                        ; switch variable to check if turn_number has the same value as
;ticket_number
  current_collector                     ; switch variable to identify a single turtle to update for
  CollectorHLocation                    ; switch variable to let home_location be read by other turtles
  CollectorCLocation                    ; switch variable to let waterpoint locations be read by other
turtles
  carry_water                           ; switch variable to let carry_amount be read by households
  To_Carry                              ; switch variable to let pump know how much water was taken
;PumpBreakdownVolume                   ; Amount of water a pump can produce before it breaks down
;NumberOfPumpsBroken                   ; Number of pumps that are not working at the moment
  max_queueP                            ; switch variable to let pump know what max_queue is of
collector
  collection_timeP                      ; switch variable to let pump know with the collectiontime is of a
collector
  enough_water?                         ; check if they have enough water, true or false
;Random_setup?                         ; model gets set up with random variables
;RandomWaterVolume                     ; the extra random volume after which a water point breaks down
  BadLevelList
  Average_ServiceLevel
]
```

```
breed [households household]           ; agent household
breed [waterpoints waterpoint]         ; agent waterpoint
breed [watercollectors watercolletor] ; agent watercollector
```

```
Patches-own                            ; variables owned by patches
[
  patch_has_hh?                         ; wether there is a household at a patch
  patch_has_wp?                         ; wether there is a waterpoint at a patch
  HH_density_radius                     ; wat the household density radius is
]
```

households-own ; variables owned by households

```
[
  household-locationH ; their location
  water_amount ; the amount of water that is currently at the household
  service_level ; the service level calculated by amount of water and time needed
to collect water
  number_residents ; each household has a number of residents
  needed_water ; each household needs a certain amount of water depending on
the number of residents
  water_service ; percentage water/needed water
  end_collecting_time
  start_collecting_time
  Total_Collecting_Time_Day
  Total_Collections_Day
  one_collecting_time
]
```

waterpoints-own ; variables owned by water points

```
[
  working-rate ; at what rate a waterpoint is working : 1 = working 0 = not
working
  Moment_Broken ; the exact tick when a water point breaks down
  waterpoint_locationP ; their location
  ticket_counter ; ticketcounter shows how many watercollectors there are at a
waterpoint
  turn_number ; turnnumber shows witch number can fetch water, when it is
their turn
  queue_length ; The lenth (in time) of the queue
  Water_Delivered ; amount of water collected from this water point
]
```

watercollectors-own ; variables owned by water collectors

```
[
  home_location ; the household that is their home
  walking-speed ; the speed the watercollectors walk with
  watercollection_status ; the status they have during the day ; outgoing, collecting-water,
redirecting, returnhome etc.
  waterpoint_locationC ; This shows the location of the waterpoint they go to to fetch
water
;collection_time ; the time it takes to pump water
  end_of_collectiontime ; this is the time a watercollector finishes pumping water
  ticket_number ; the number they got at the waterpoint to wait in queue and to
fetch water
  carry_amount ; the amount of water they carry
  max_queueC ; The maximum time they want to spend queuing
]
```

```

researched?          ; if a queue is to long they search for another water point
]

to setup              ; if you push the setup button these actions will take place
clear-all            ; everything will be erased
reset-ticks           ; ticks will start at 0

set BadLevelList []
set ref_distance 25  ; the distance for a patch is 25 meter
set new_ticket 0     ; the start of the model has no new tickets
set Days_running 0   ; at the start the days running is zero

setup_households      ;households will be setup
setup_waterpoints     ; water points will be setup
setup_watercollectors ; water collectors will be setup
if random_setup? = true ; setup a random situation with a random number of water
amount at households
  [set NumberOfPumpsBroken random 15
  ask waterpoints with [working-rate = 0
  [ set Moment_broken random -18000]
  ask households
  [ set water_amount random 120]
  ask waterpoints
  [ set water_delivered random 90000] ; and a random number of water taken from the
water points
  ]
end

to go                  ; to start running the model the following actions will be taken
if count waterpoints with [working-rate = 1] < 2 ; if only 2 water points are working
[stop]                ; the model stops working
determine_time_day    ; Determine what the time of the day is and how many days the
model is running
Check_Pump_Repair
outgoing              ; when the watercollector moves to a waterpoint
arrive                ; when the watercollector arrives at a waterpoint
re_search             ; If a queue is to long they will search for a water point with a
shorter queue
redirect              ; when the watercollector is redirected from a waterpoint to
another waterpoint (if queue is too long or if waterpoint is broken)
queue                 ; the actual waiting at the pump
collect_water         ; collecting water
return_home           ; returning home
standby               ; water collector is standby at home and dropped of his water
tick                  ; time passes one tick

end

```

;THIS PROCEDURE SETS UP THE HOUSEHOLD IN A SIMPLE TWO_STAGE SPREAD ALLOWING FOR CLUSTERING

```

to setup_households
  ask patches [ set patch_has_hh? false ]
  ask n-of Nbr_of_HH_clusters patches [ ;Nbr_of_HH_clusters determines the total number of
household CLUSTERS
  Ask n-of Nbr_of_HH_in_cluster patches in-radius Radius_of_cluster ;Nbr_of_HH_in_cluster
determines the total number of household in each cluster
  [set patch_has_hh? true] ;declare patch has household
] ;close "ask n-of ..."
set-default-shape households "house" ;set that households look like a house
ask patches [if patch_has_hh? = true ;set only one house on each patch with
patch_has_hh = 1
  [sprout-households 1 ; a household will be 'build'
  [set color brown ;colour the house brown
  set size 6 ;set the size of the house
  set water_amount 0 ; start with 0 water
  set number_residents 6 ; they have 6 residents per household
  set needed_water (number_residents * 15) ; people need 15 liter per person
  set Total_collecting_Time_Day 0 ; to set up the model collecting time starts
;at 0
  set Total_Collections_Day 0 ; to set up the model the total collections
;start at 0
  set Service_level 4 ; to set up the model the service levels
;starts at 4
  ] ; end set color brown
  ] ; end sprout households 1
  ] ; end if patche_has_hh?
end

```

```

to setup_watercollectors ; how the water collectors are setup
set-default-shape watercollectors "person" ; set watercollectors to look like persons
ask patches [ if patch_has_hh? = true ; if a patch has a household there will be one
watercollector
  [sprout-watercollectors 1 ; water collector is born
  [set color blue ; color of watercollectors
  set size 6 ; size of watercollectors
  hide-turtle
  set home_location patch-here ; giving their household the sign home_location
  set watercollection_status "standby" ; start of the day with status standby
  set walking-speed (average_speed + random 2.7) ; set the walking speed
  set ticket_number 1 ; the first ticket number that will be given by a water point is
1

```

```

set carry_amount 0 ; the amount of water they carry is at the
beginning of the model 0
set max_queueC (20 / 60)
set Waterpoint_locationC [Waterpoint_locationP] of min-one-of waterpoints [distance myself]
; sets the waterpoint they have to walk to as the waterpoint closest to their home_location
set researched? false ; they haven't been redirected yet
] ; end set color yellow
] ; end sprout watercollectors 1
] ; end if patch_has_hh? = true

end

to setup_waterpoints
ask patches [set patch_has_wp? false] ; first ask all the patches to have no waterpoints
ask n-of Nbr_of_waterpoints patches ; ask a number of waterpoints (can be changed in
interface)
[set patch_has_wp? true] ; to say they have a water point
set-default-shape waterpoints "handpump" ; set shape of waterpoint is 'pump'
ask patches
[if patch_has_wp? = true ; if we say the patch has a waterpoint we will
sprout a turtle waterpoint
[spout-waterpoints 1
[set waterpoint_locationP patch-here ; give the location of the waterpoint as
waterpoint_locationP
set color sky ; give the color sky
set label-color white ; give the label-color white
set size 8 ; set the size
] ; end set waterpoint_locationP
] ; end spout-waterpoints 1
] ; end if patch_has_wp? = true
ask waterpoints
[set working-rate 1 ; ask all the waterpoints to set their workingrate at
1 (working)
set turn_number 1 ; and ask them to set their first turn_number at 1
set Water_Delivered 0 ; No water delivered at the start
set ticket_counter 0 ; ask them to set their ticket_counter at 0 at the
start
] ; end set working-rate 1
ask n-of NumberOfPumpsBroken waterpoints; ask a number of waterpoints (number can be
changed at interface)
[set working-rate 0 ; to set their workingrate at 0 (not-working) and
turn red
set color red
set Moment_Broken Ticks ; If a water point breaks down the Moment_Broken
is the number of ticks at that time
] ; end set working-rate 0

```

end

```
To determine_time_day ; to determine the current time and day
if floor (ticks / 900 ) > Days_runnin ; 900 ticks per day, 60 ticks per hour so the day ends at
21:00 (6+ 15*60)
[set Days_running Days_running + 1 ; if 900 ticks have past the day will go up
ask waterpoints
[set ticket_counter 0 ; every day ticket counter starts at 0
set turn_number 1] ; every day turn number starts at 0
ask households
[let Average_Collection_time 1
if Total_Collections_Day > 0
[set Average_Collection_Time ((Total_Collecting_Time_Day * 60) / Total_Collections_Day)]
; the ;average collecting time is calculated
ifelse (water_service >= 50) ; if they have more than 50% of their needed water
[if Average_Collection_time <= 10 ; and their average collection time is smaller than
10 ;minutes
[set Service_level 1 ; they have service level 1 and colour green
set color green]
if (Average_Collection_Time > 10) and (Average_Collection_Time <= 60)
[set Service_level 2 ; level 2 colour yellow
set color yellow]
if Average_Collection_Time > 60 ; level 3 colour orange
[set Service_level 3
set color orange]
] ; end if Average_Collection_time <= 10
[set Service_level 4 ; level 4 colour red
set color red
if member? self BadLevelList = false
[set BadLevelList lput self BadlevelList]
] ; end of the ifelse (water_service
set Total_Collections_Day 0 ; every day the total number of collections starts at
0
set total_collecting_time_day 0 ; if they have more water than they needed, they
will
ifelse (water_amount - needed_water) > 0 ; keep water for the next day
[set water_amount (water_amount - needed_water)] ; if not they start the next day
[set water_amount 0] ; with 0 water
]
Set Average_ServiceLevel ((count households with [service_level = 1]) + 2 * (count
households with [service_level = 2]) + 3 * (count households with [service_level = 3]) + 4 *
(count households with [ service_level = 4]))/ 780
] ; end set days_running
set Time_of_day ( 6 + ((ticks - (900 * Days_running))/ 60)) ; day starts at 6 and ends at 21 so 15
hours
```

```

each 60 ticks
end

to Check_Pump_Repair ; to check if a pump can be repaired
Ask waterpoints
[if working-rate < 1 ; check if the pump is broken
  [if (Ticks - Moment_Broken) > (PumpRepairTime * 900) ; if the current ticks - the ticks of the
moment the pump broke down is bigger then the repair time
    [set working-rate 1 ; the working-rate becomes 1
      set color blue ; the color will be blue
      set Water_Delivered 0] ; and the water_delivered will be set to 0 again
    ] ; end if (ticks-moment_broken
  ] ; end if working-rate < 1
end

to outgoing
ask watercollectors
[if watercollection_status = "outgoing"
  [show-turtle ; if the turtle leaves the house and is outgoing it is showed
on the interface
  face waterpoint_locationC ; they will face the location they have to go to and step 1
  patch further
  let thedistance (distance Waterpoint_locationC) ; we let the distance they
;need to cover to a waterpoint be thedistance
  [ifelse thedistance >= walking-speed ; if this distance is bigger
than their ; walkingspeed they will walk with their walking-speed
    [forward walking-speed]
    [forward thedistance] ; if the distance is smaller they will walk only the distance
  if Time_of_Day > 18.5 ; if they are outgoing and the time of the ;day is later than
18:30 they will go home
  [set watercollection_status "return_home"]
  if ([patch_has_wp?] of patch-here = true) and (Waterpoint_LocationC = patch-here)
    ; see if the patch they are on has a waterpoint and if it is
the location they had to go to (waterpoint_locationC), then they have arrived
  [set watercollection_status "arrived"]
  ] ; end face waterpoint_locationC
] ; end if watercollection_status = outgoing
end

to arrive
ask watercollectors
[Set Current_Collector WHO ; to be able to give the new ticketnumber to a single
collector
  if watercollection_status = "arrived" ; check if they are arriving and if they have
  [ifelse researched? = true ; searched for another pump allready
    [set watercollection_status "queue" ; they will queue
      ask waterpoints-here
      [set ticket_counter ticket_counter + 1 ; the ticket number goes up by one

```

```

set new_ticket ticket_counter
if ticket_counter < 60 ; check the use intensity of pumps
    [set color green] ; less than 60 users per day: green
if (ticket_counter > 60) and (ticket_counter < 120)
    [set color yellow] ; less than 120 per day: yellow
if ticket_counter > 120
    [set color orange] ; more than 120 per day: orange
set ticket_number new_ticket]
[set max_queueP max_queueC ; set max_queue of collector into global
variable to read by waterpoints
set collection_timeP (collection_time / 60) ; collection time is in minutes on the
interface in the model it is number/60 ticks = minutes
ask waterpoints-here
[set queue_length (((ticket_counter + 1) - turn_number) * collection_timeP) ;
queue_length is the number of watercollectors here * the collection_time of the collectors
ifelse working-rate = 1 ; check if the waterpoint works if so
    [ifelse queue_length > max_queueP ; check if queue is to long if so re_search for
another pump
        [ask turtle Current_Collector
            [set watercollection_status "re_search"
                set color blue] ; end set watercollectionstatus research
            ] ; end ask turtle current_collector
        [ask turtle Current_Collector ; ask the watercollector at this patch that just
arrived (and only that one)
            [set watercollection_status "queue"
                ask waterpoints-here
                    [set ticket_counter ticket_counter + 1 ; ask the waterpoint here to set his
ticket_counter 1 higher since a collector has allready taken a ticket
                        set new_ticket ticket_counter ; change ticket_counter to global variable
                        if ticket_counter < 60
                            [set color green]
                        if (ticket_counter > 60) and (ticket_counter < 120)
                            [set color yellow]
                        if ticket_counter > 120
                            [set color orange]
                        ] ; end set ticket_counter
                    set ticket_number new_ticket ; take the global variable new_ticket and set it
even with ticket_number
                ] ; end set watercollection_status queue
            ] ; end ask turtle currentcollector
        ] ; end ifelse queue_length
    [ask turtle Current_Collector ; if the waterpoint doesn't work
        [set watercollection_status "redirecting" ; let (only this) watercollector be
redirected
            ] ; end set watercollection status redirected
        ] ; end ask turtle current_collector
    ] ; end set queue_length (count watercoll-here

```

```

]] ; end set max_queueP max_queuec
] ; end set current_collector who
end

```

to redirect ; if a waterpoint is broken a watercollector will be redirected to another working waterpoint

Ask Watercollectors

```

[if watercollection_status = "redirecting"
  [set CollectorCLocation patch-here ; shows what the current position is of the
watercollectors and sets it to CollectorClocation

```

```

  set CollectorHLocation Home_Location ; makes a global variable the same as
Home_location so it can be read by other turtles

```

```

  set Waterpoint_LocationC [Waterpoint_locationP] of
    min-one-of waterpoints with [working-rate = 1]
    [((Distance CollectorHLocation) + (Distance CollectorCLocation))]

```

; asks what the minimum distance is (from a working waterpoint to a household + from a working waterpoint to a watercollector)

; CollectorHlocation is the location of the household (home_location) CollectorClocation of the watercollector

```

  set watercollection_status "outgoing" ; if it is redirected to another waterpoint it will be
outgoing again

```

```

] ; end set collectorClocation patch-here

```

```

] ; end if watercollection_status = redirecting

```

end

to re_search ; to search for another water point with a small queue

ask watercollectors

```

[if watercollection_status = "re_search"

```

```

  [set CollectorCLocation patch-here ; we set the location of the watercollector
CollectorClocation

```

```

  set CollectorHLocation Home_Location ; we set the homelocation of the collector as
CollectorHlocation

```

```

  set waterpoint_locationC [waterpoint_locationP] of min-one-of
    waterpoints with [(waterpoint_locationP != CollectorClocation) AND (working-rate = 1)]
    [((Distance CollectorHLocation) + (Distance CollectorCLocation))]

```

; we calculate the minimum distance of a waterpoint that works

with a small queue

```

; and set this waterpoint as Waterpoint_locationC

```

```

  set watercollection_status "outgoing"

```

```

  set researched? true

```

```

] ; end set collectorClocation patch-here

```

```

] ; end if watercollection_status = research
end

to queue ; the actual queuing procedure
ask watercollectors
[if watercollection_status = "queue"
  [ask waterpoints-here ; only ask the waterpoint here, the one where the
watercollector is at
  [set current_number turn_number] ; set their turnnumber in to a global variable to check
  if current_number = ticket_number ; if the turnnumber equals the ticket_number of the
waterpoint
  [set watercollection_status "collect_water" ; if so they can collect water
  set end_of_collectiontime (Time_of_Day + (collection_time / 60)); the time they will be
finished is the current time plus the collection time
  ] ; end set watercollection status collect water
]
if Time_of_Day > 20
[set water collection_status "return_home"]
] ; end ask waterpoints-here
] ; end if watercollection status = queue
end

to collect_water
ask watercollectors
[if watercollection_status = "collect_water"
  [if Time_of_Day > end_of_collectiontime ; if the collection time is over
(end_of_collectiontime)
  [set watercollection_status "return_home" ; they will return home
  set To_Carry (15 + random 6) ; with a random amount of water between 15
and 20
  set carry_amount To_Carry ; set to_carry in a switch variable
carry_amount
  ask waterpoints-here
  [set turn_number turn_number + 1 ; if a collector leaves the pump with water the
next one can get water so the turn_number goes up
  set Water_Delivered Water_Delivered + To_Carry
  if Water_Delivered > (PumpBreakDownVolume + random RandomWaterVolume)
; If water delivered is more then the
Pumpbreakdownvolum
; plus a random number choosen at the interface the
pump breaks down
  [set working-rate 0 ; if the pump breaks down the working-rate = 0
  set color red ; the color is red
  set Moment_Broken Ticks] ; the moment of breakdown is the number of ticks
so far
  ] ; end set turn_number turn_n
  ] ; end set watercollection_status "return_home"
] ; end if time_of_day > end_of_collectiontime

```

```

] ; end if watercollection_status = 'collectwater'
end

to return_home
ask watercollectors
[if watercollection_status = "return_home" ; if they have the status return_home they
will return to their home_location
[ set waterpoint_locationC [waterpoint_locationP] of min-one-of ; if they returnhome their
waterpoints with [working-rate = 1] [distance myself] ; destination for a waterpoint will
be the closest waterpoint that works
face home_location ; they will face their home_location
let thedistance (distance home_location) ; distance to their home is
thedistance
ifelse thedistance >= walking-speed ; if this distance is larger then their
walking speed
[forward walking-speed] ; they walk with the walking speed
[forward thedistance] ; if not they will walk the distance
leftover
if ([patch_has_hh?] of patch-here = true) and (home_location = patch-here) ; if they arrive,
they check if the patch has a household and if it is their household
[ask watercollectors-here
[set watercollection_status "standby" ; if they are home they will be
standby until they go for water again
ask households-here
[set end_collecting_time Time_of_Day ; if they arrive home this will be
the end of their collection time
set one_collecting_time (end_collecting_time - start_collecting_time) ; the one-time
collection is calculated
set Total_Collecting_Time_Day Total_Collecting_Time_Day + (end_collecting_time -
start_collecting_time) ; the total collection time of the day is calculated
set Total_Collections_Day Total_Collections_Day + 1
] ; end set end_collecting_time
] ; end set watercollection status standby
] ; end ask watercollectors-here
] ; end set waterpoint_location
]
end

```

```

to standby
ask watercollectors
[if watercollection_status = "standby" ; if the water collectors are standby they will
drop of their water
[ hide-turtle
set carry_water carry_amount ; sets carry water into a global variable so it can
be read by household
set researched? false

```

```

ask households-here
  [set water_amount (water_amount + carry_water) ; current amount of water of a
household will be increased with the water of the watercollector
  set water_service ((water_amount / needed_water) * 100) ; water service is the
percentage of water they have compared to water they need
  set enough_water? (water_amount > needed_water)
]
set carry_amount 0 ; the water of the watercollector will be set to 0 again
if Time_of_Day < 18.5 and ((random-float 1 > 0.96) ; so people won't directly leave the
house again
and (enough_water? = false))
  [set watercollection_status "outgoing"
ask households-here
  [set start_collecting_time Time_of_Day] ; if they go out this will be the start time of
their collection
  ] ; end set watercollection status outgoing
] ; end set carry_water
] ; end if watercollection status = standby
end

```

Appendix C: Test results

		Correlations		
		avservlevel	numberpumps	repairtime
avservlevel	Pearson Correlation	1	-,580**	,177
	Sig. (2-tailed)		,001	,349
	N	30	30	30
numberpumps	Pearson Correlation	-,580**	1	,500**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,001		,005
	N	30	30	30
repairtime	Pearson Correlation	,177	,500**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,349	,005	
	N	30	30	30

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Figure 12: *correlation of service level, pumps and repair time*

		Correlations		
		numberpumps	repairtime	avLevel4
numberpumps	Pearson Correlation	1	,302	-,675**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		,059	,000
	N	40	40	40
repairtime	Pearson Correlation	,302	1	,290
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,059		,070
	N	40	40	40
avLevel4	Pearson Correlation	-,675**	,290	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,000	,070	
	N	40	40	40

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Figure 13: *correlation of service level 4, pumps and repair*

Scenario 2: households with service level 4										
	test 1	test 2	test 3	test 4	test 5	test 6	test 7	test 8	test 9	test 10
min	1	5	0	6	0	21	0	0	2	2
max	218	330	130	217	258	242	155	304	320	152
average percentage: 14,3%										
average number: 118,15										
service level										
	test 1	test 3	test 5	test 7	test 9					
	2,923	2,931	3,001	2,944	2,978					
average service level: 2,955										
Scenario 3: households with service level 4										
	test 1	test 2	test 3	test 4	test 5	test 6	test 7	test 8	test 9	test 10
min	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	25	21	0
max	68	95	161	135	228	180	32	240	205	80
average percentage: 9,43%										
average number: 73,6										
service level										
	test 1	test 3	test 5	test 7	test 9					
	2,982	2,91	2,892	2,845	2,941					
average service level: 2,914										
Scenario 4: households with service level 4										
	test 1	test 2	test 3	test 4	test 5	test 6	test 7	test 8	test 9	test 10
min	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	2	1	3
max	137	211	166	278	162	91	85	194	150	163
average percentage: 10,54%										
average number: 82,25										
service level										
	test 1	test 3	test 5	test 7	test 9					
	2,937	2,996	2,917	2,985	3,117					
average service level: 2,990										

Table 3: Maximum, minimum and average of households with level 4

One-Sample Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
avservlevel	40	2,4908	,25171	,03980
numberpumps	40	20,7500	4,82382	,76271
repairtime	40	16,6250	4,13514	,65382

One-Sample Test

	Test Value = 0					
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
avservlevel	62,585	39	,000	2,49075	2,4103	2,5712
numberpumps	27,206	39	,000	20,75000	19,2073	22,2927
repairtime	25,427	39	,000	16,62500	15,3025	17,9475

Variables Entered/Removed^a

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	repairtime, numberpumps ^b	.	Enter

a. Dependent Variable: avservlevel

b. All requested variables entered.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,834 ^a	,696	,680	,14241

a. Predictors: (Constant), repairtime, numberpumps

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1,720	2	,860	42,416	,000 ^b
	Residual	,750	37	,020		
	Total	2,471	39			

a. Dependent Variable: avservlevel

b. Predictors: (Constant), repairtime, numberpumps

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	2,864	,115		24,902	,000
numberpumps	-,046	,005	-,890	-8,915	,000
repairtime	,035	,006	,583	5,841	,000

a. Dependent Variable: avservlevel

Figure 14: *test results of one-sample t-test all data combined.*